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Properties of Interfacial Layers in Nanoparticle-Surfactant Dispersions

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Owing to their ability to adsorb at the nanoparticle (NP) surface, suitable surfactants can be added to NP dispersions, in order to create amphiphilic complexes that, in turn, can adsorb at the liquid interface. This is a straightforward and cheap method in alternative to the use of properly designed NP, such as Janus NPs or to complicate NP surface modifications based on physical methods. In spite of the apparent simplicity, these particle-surfactant systems present however complex behaviors in terms of the structural, thermodynamic and kinetic properties, influencing the main mechanical properties of the interface, such as interfacial tension and the dilational rheology.

We report here a set of case studies, illustrating such complexity and the benefit deriving from investigations based on different experimental approaches, such as, dynamic surface/interfacial tension and dilational rheology, Ellipsometry and Brewster Angle Microscopy.

These case studies, concerned with the utilisation of different types of NPs, ionic and non-ionic surfactants, liquid-liquid and liquid-air interfaces, allows elucidating the processes involved in the formation of these layers, rationalising common features and specific behaviour.

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